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BEGINNING: Giving birth to a child and taking care of it is a very responsible job. At the same time in line, raising righteous child – meaning healthy, with a board worldview, himself get along with others and respond appropriately to the events around them it means educating a person who will receive. Education is the most important and sacred thing in a parent's life and is an art that lasts a lifetime. Especially in the currents, ideological ideas, various vices trying to exert their influence. During this period, the responsibility of each father and mother becomes heavier. Child rearing – continuous process. This requires patience, satisfaction and trust.

PARENTAL INFLUENCE It is worth noting that, the family is the main need. Peace, happiness and joy can only be found in the family. Alternatively, a parent is a child's first teacher. The child sees from his parents, learns and grows up. Parents have a great responsibility in raising a child. Children are mentally mature, physically healthy depends on parents and teachers. School – is the child's second home. The

ALL OF THE BEST THINGS FOR MY CHILD!

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on how to attention paid to children and child education in recent years in the territory of our Republic, in particular on a global scale.

child taking into account the characteristics of his physical, psychological and genetic development in upbringing need to get. According to experts, a child has the qualities of his parents. It is emphasized that although he does embody it, he definitely gets two main things from them.

These are:

AFFECTION

EDUCATION

LOVE - means the beautiful feelings of support, help and being loved.

EDUCATION – is necessary for all knowledge, rules, values, socialization of a person see all traditions.

So, a child needs parents from birth to adulthood therefore, a lot of attention is required from parents. Although parents are children, a child is not an exact copy of the father or mother, even if they consider it a part of themselves. Every child is a person with character. That is why it is significant to raise a child, there are recommendations to be made:

1.If the parents give the child as much affection and love as he or she needs, his

self- confidence will increase and he will not feel sad and fear is reduced.

2.A child who sees enough affection and sincerity in the family has moral values seeks to embody.

3.Children who are often punished with beatings at home and are always considered guilty are their parents they feel like a hurtful naughty child.

4.If the parent has a calm and patient relationship with the child as much as possible, to him there is no need to give excessive fertilizer and reminders.

5.There is no room for trying too hard to be a good parent. There is enough sincerity in this matter.

6.When your child misbehaves, tell them, “YOU DO NOT DO WHAT YOU SAID, WHEN YOU ARE HUMAN, YOU ALWAYS WORRY US” , it is not correct to throw dice. If the parent gives the usual rebuke and dices, the result is the child he does not believe in his family, to solve the problems in his life together does not seek on the contrary, a parent is a child who listens to his child and tries to understand him keeps his honor in front of his eyes. Unfortunately, there are not a few parents who have the concept of “MODERN LIFE” and lifestyle today. According to the current statistics, the

average amount of time that parents spend with their children around the world is 12 minutes for fathers and for mothers it is 30 minutes. What a sad situation. Performance and material to forget our child or spend less time to meet our needs cannot be an excuse. Let’s put everything aside and devote time to the child and we need to communicate. We should treat the child and his world accordingly.

CONCLUSION: From the above, it should be noted that every child is a world. They also have their own unique behavior. They are our future and perspective. At this point, “Us always another important issue that comes to mind is related to the manners, behavior and in a word, worldview of our youth. Today is very fast changing. Who will feel these changes the most – youth. Okay, let the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time his identity do not forget who are we, and what are the descendants of great people, the call is in their hearts let it always resonate and encourage you to stay true to yourself. At what cost? We can reach EDUCATION, EDUCATION and only EDUCATION will be achieved “ , says President SH.M.MIRZIYOYEV.

References:

1. Turkish psychological scientist Vakhaddin Yasar. “Parenting is not a toy”.